

Acetalisation Reaction in Micro Assay of Atorvastatin Calcium Trihydrate Using 2-Hydroxynaphthylaldehyde

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ABSTRACT

The acetylation reaction is an important reaction that includes the formation of acetal or ketal-colored products from the reaction of alcoholic groups with aldehyde or ketone compounds. The present suggested method consists of a direct spectrophotometric method for estimating atorvastatin calcium trihydrate through the nucleophilic addition reaction (acetal formation) where atorvastatin as carboxylic acid with two hydroxyl groups react with 2-hydroxynaphthylaldehyde in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid to give colored product has a higher absorption at wavelength 580 nm. The relation between absorbance and concentration was linear within the concentration range of 0.1 - 5.0 µg / ml, and the molar absorptivity was $5.1412 \times 10^4 \text{ l.mol}^{-1}.\text{cm}^{-1}$. The proposed method was successfully applied to estimate calcium atorvastatin in its pharmaceutical preparations (tablets).

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1. Introduction

The nucleophilic addition reaction also known as the acetylation reaction, it is an organic reaction that includes the formation of acetal or ketal, through one of the reactions of the nucleophilic addition of m alcohols to an aldehyde or a ketone. The resulting acetal compound is more stable and does not hydrolyze in acidic or basic media. It can also be easily isolated or extracted with organic solvents [1].

Atorvastatin belongs to the set of statin drugs, and it is major uses to treat high levels of cholesterol (LDL) and also the triglycerides in the blood and aids to increase high-density lipoprotein (HDL), hypercholesterolemia affected by genetic influences or due to wrong diet and nonexistence of exercise, and it is also used in cases of hypercholesterolemia. Lipoproteins, atherosclerosis, hypertriglyceridemia, and radiation nephropathy [2].

One of the most important salts of atorvastatin is atorvastatin calcium trihydrate (ATO-Ca), which is the subject of our current research. It is an organic substance in the form of a white to yellowish powder. It has acceptable solubility in water, especially in aqueous solutions at $\text{pH} \leq 4$ and less. It also has little solubility in ethanol 96%, it dissolves very freely in methanol. It has the molecular formula $\text{C}_{66}\text{H}_{74}\text{CaF}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_{13}$ or $(\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{34}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_5)_2\text{Ca} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Its chemical composition is as shown in Figure1 and its molecular weight is 1209.4 g / mol. [3].

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Fig. 1 . The chemical structure of ATO.

Various techniques have been used in the assay of atorvastatin: electrochemical including cyclic voltammetry[4-6]. The high performance liquid chromatography[7-10], flow injection analyse[11], fluorescence analysis[12] and capillary electrophoresis [13].

Although the above techniques are characterized by high sensitivity, and it is possible to estimate the compound under study in the presence of other medicinal compounds, the spectroscopic methods remain easy and their devices are available in most laboratories, and they are also cheap and easier to deal with. Therefore, many studies are available in the literature using the spectrophotometer.

The spectrophotometric methods included using various reactions and reagents such as condensation reaction (Schiff's base) using DMAB [14], oxidative coupling using crystal violet, [KBr: KBrO₃] in the acidic medium [15], nucleophilic substitution using NQS at pH=11.5 [15], Ion-pair complex using BTB, BCP, and BCG dyes [16], Ion-pair complex using BTB [17], charge transfer complexation [18], Oxidative Coupling using MBTH with FeCl₃ and nucleophilic substitution using NQS [19], oxidative coupling using 2,4 DNP [20], hydrolysis then diazo-coupling with β-naphthol [21].

2. Experimental

2.1. Apparatus

Spectral measurements and absorbance readings were carried out using a JASCOV-630 spectrometer, and glass cells with a light path of 1 cm were used.

2.2. The chemicals reagent and solvents

The analytical reagents used in the present procedure were of high purity.

2.2.1. Solutions

-Atorvastatin calcium trihydrate (ATO-Ca) Solution, 100 µg/ml.

This solution was prepared by dissolving 0.0100 g of the pure ATO-Ca (produced by the Indian company ATRI and supplied by Samarra Pharmaceutical Company) in 20 ml of methanol and shaking well, then completing the volume to 100 ml with the same solvent.

-The reagent solution is 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde (2-HNA), 1%

Dissolve 1.0000 g of pure 2-HNA in an amount of absolute ethanol in a volumetric flask of 100 ml, then fill the volume with absolute ethanol. It is kept in a dark container and kept in a cool place.

-Pharmaceutical solution LipoNeer tablets, 100 µg/ml.

The tablets are produced by the Iraqi PioNeer company, as each tablet contains 20 mg of ARO-Ca. The average weight of 10 tablets was 246.9 mg. The 10 tablets were crushed and mixed well, and the weight equivalent to 0.0100 g of pure ATO-Ca from the powder was taken dissolved in 50 ml of methanol, and shaken in the solution well then top up to 100 ml of methanol.

-Pharmaceutical solution ATEROZ tablets

Tablets produced by the Turkish company Cila Bilim. Each tablet contains 10 mg of ATO-Ca, with a weight of 10 tablets and an average weight of 55.0 mg. The solution was prepared using the same previous method used in preparing the LipoNeer tablet solution.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Principle of method

The method depends on the formation of acetylation from the reaction of the hydroxyl groups in ATO-Ca with the carbonyl group in the aldehyde in an acidic medium to give a colored product that gives an absorption spectrum in the visible region. Therefore, a preliminary study was conducted to choose the best aldehyde compound.

3.2. Studying optimal conditions

All components of the main reaction have been studied and the optimal one has been chosen.

2.2.1. The type of aldehyde used in the reaction

Taking 2.0 ml of a previously prepared 100 μg ATO-Ca solution and adding 2.0 ml of 1% aldehydes and 1.0 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid and taking the spectrum for each solution against its blank solution after supplementing the volume with methanol (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of the reaction of ATO-Ca with different aldehydes.

From the results of Fig. 2, $\Delta\lambda_{\text{max}}$, and the molar absorption coefficient were calculated, and the results were recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: The results of using different aldehyde reagents.

Type of Aldehyde .5	4. λ_{max}	3. $\Delta\lambda^*$	Absorbance .2	$\epsilon: \text{l.mole}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$.1
2-Chlorobenzaldehyde .10	385 .9	43 .8	0.890 .7	5.1415×10^4 .6
4-Methoxybenzaldehyde .15	432 .14	58 .13	0.228 .12	1.3171×10^4 .11
Vanillin .20	540 .19	57 .18	0.647 .17	3.7377×10^4 .16
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde .25	550 .24	60 .23	0.574 .22	3.3160×10^4 .21
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde .30	580 .29	90 .28	0.752 .27	4.3443×10^4 .26
4-Bromobanzaldehyde .32			N.R. .31	

* $\Delta\lambda$ (Colour constant) = $\lambda_{\text{max product}} - \lambda_{\text{Blank}}$

From the results shown in Table 1, it was found that the 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (2-HNA) reagent at a concentration of 1.0 % gives high absorption of the formed product and the color contrast value was good. $\Delta\lambda_{\text{max}} = 90 \text{ nm}$ compared to

other aldehydes used.

3.2.2. Study the amount of reagent 2-HNA

The effect of the amount of 2-HNA on the absorbance of the colored product was studied by adding increasing volumes of the reagent solution from 0.5 to 3.0 ml to different concentrations of 1-12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ATO-Ca and then adding 0.5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid and waiting for 10 minutes until the color appeared. Complete the volume to the mark with methanol and measure the absorbance of these solutions against the blank solution at the wavelength of 580 nm as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The effect of adding different amounts of aldehyde on the absorbance of the colored product.

ml of 2-HNA,1.0%	Absorbance $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ATO-Ca						R^2
	1	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.0	
0.5	0.075	0.098	0.120	0.119	0.101	0.094	0.0379
1	0.109	0.142	0.164	0.186	0.190	0.183	0.6680
1.5	0.153	0.186	0.214	0.251	0.284	0.318	0.9709
2	0.180	0.230	0.279	0.329	0.379	0.427	0.9652
2.5	0.185	0.247	0.361	0.448	0.583	0.701	0.9937
3.0	0.154	0.233	0.282	0.473	0.571	0.630	0.9698

It was found from the results fixed in Table 2 that a volume of 2.5 ml of 2-HNA gives the highest absorbance of the colored product, so it was adopted in subsequent experiments.

3.2.3. Effect of acid quality

The reaction does not occur in a basic medium, so it needs a strong acid medium because the reaction is slow in a weak acid medium, as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Effect of acid on the course of the reaction and the nature of the product formed.

Therefore, different strong acids were used to choose the best acid by taking 0.5 ml of a solution of 100 μg of Ca-ATO and adding 2.5 ml of 2-HNA, and adding 1.0 ml of different concentrated acids in a series of 10 ml-volumetric flasks (with caution when adding the acids and taking into account their cooling under tap water and light shaking due to the high temperature of the solutions and waiting for 15 minutes to complete the reaction), the volume was supplemented with methanol, the absorbance reading of the solutions against their blank solutions,

as in Table 3.

Table 3: Effect of the acid type on the absorbance of the colored product.

Type of conc. acid	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HNO ₃	H ₃ PO ₄
Absorbance	0.085	0.378	No. Reaction	0.239

Concentrated sulfuric acid was chosen as the best acid to give it the highest absorbance of the colored product formed.

3.2.4. Effect of the amount of concentrated sulfuric acid

Different volumes of sulfuric acid were taken from 0.2-2 ml, and the rest of the reaction components were added as previously mentioned in volumes and sequence, and the absorbance was measured for the colored product of the ATO-Ca solution at a concentration of 5 µg / ml against its blank solution at a wavelength of 580 nm, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: The effect of the amount of sulfuric acid on absorbance

ml of H ₂ SO ₄	0.2	0.5	0.8	1.0	1.5	2.0
Absorbance	0.203	0.301	0.361	0.381	0.293	0.273

The results of Table 4 show that a volume of 1.0 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid gives the highest absorbance of the formed colored product, so it was adopted in subsequent experiments.

3.2.5. Study the sequence of addition

The effect of the sequence of additions was studied by taking 0.5 ml of a 100 µg ATO-Ca / ml solution, and the rest of the reaction components were added as previously mentioned in volumes and the method was applied with the previously used volumes and sequences, the results as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: The effect of the sequence of additions.

No	Order of addition	Absorbance
I	ATO-Ca + H ₂ SO ₄ + 2-HNA	0.332
II	ATO-Ca + 2-HNA + H ₂ SO ₄	0.370
III	2-HNA + H ₂ SO ₄ + ATO-Ca	0.379

The results of Table 5 show that the addition sequence (III) gives the best intensity of the product formed, and this explains the importance of the presence of the acid as a catalyst for the reaction, as it makes the carbonyl group in the aldehyde (reagent) more electrophilic and more ready for nucleophile addition than before alcohol, as explained previously in the equation for the effect of acid, Scheme 1 above.

3.2.6. Study the effect of time on the formation of product

To find the reaction time, 2.5 ml of 2-HNA reagent was added it to each flask in the series of 10 ml volumetric flasks, add 1.0 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid, shake lightly, add 0.5 ml of a solution of 100 µg of ATO-Ca and wait for different times, then complete the volume with methanol and read the absorbance at the wavelength of 580 nm. The results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The effect of time on the composition of the colored product.

Time, min before dilution	Immediately	2	5	10	15	20	25
Absorbance	0.263	0.308	0.362	0.383	0.384	0.380	0.381

The results showed that to obtain the highest absorbance, waiting 15 minutes before supplementing the volume up to the

mark. Therefore, it was adopted to leave the solutions at the laboratory temperature for 15 minutes in the subsequent experiments before filling the volume with absolute methanol.

3.2.7. Study the effect of solvents

The effect of a number of different organic solvents on the resulting product was studied by taking a series of volumetric flasks with a capacity of 10 ml, taking 2.5 ml of reagent 2-HNA, adding 1.0 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid, lightly shaking carefully, adding 1.2 ml of a 100 μg of ATO-Ca solution, and waiting. for 15 minutes to complete the reaction, and then dilute the reaction product for these solutions and measure the absorption against the blank solution of these solutions, as shown in Fig. 3 and Table 7.

Fig. 3: Absorption spectra of 12.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Ca-ATO reacted with 2-HNA using different solvents.

Table 7: The effect of different solvents on the absorption of the formed colored product.

Solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	Absorbance	$\epsilon: \text{l. mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$
Ethanol	580	0.678	6.528×10^4
Methanol	580	0.610	5.873×10^4
Acetone	580	0.570	5.268×10^4
Acetonitrile	580	0.543	5.018×10^4
DMF	583	0.324	2.994×10^4
DMSO	582	0.175	1.617×10^4
Distilled water		Turbid	

In the results of Table 7, it was found that the absolute ethanol solvent gives the highest absorbance of the formed colored product, so it was adopted in subsequent experiments instead of methanol.

3.2.7. Study of reaction stability

The effect of time on the stability of two different concentrations of ATO-Ca was studied and the results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: The effect of time on the absorbance of product.

Time, min.	Absorbance μg of ATO-Ca / ml	
	5.0	15.0
2	0.312	0.795
5	0.332	0.815
10	0.339	0.818

15	0.340	0.822
20	0.342	0.823
25	0.344	0.822
30	0.343	0.824
35	0.343	0.825
40	0.344	0.825
45	0.345	0.826
50	0.348	0.828
60	0.349	0.830

The results in Table 8 indicate that the colored product gives a stable and analytically acceptable absorbance reading after 5 minutes of completing the additions and remains stable for another 55 minutes.

3.3. Final absorption spectrum

To find the absorption spectrum, the optimum conditions established in Table 9 are followed by taking a volume of 2.5 ml of 2-HNA (1.0%) and adding 1.0 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid carefully with light shaking and adding 1.20 ml of a solution of 100 μg of ATO-Ca, then cooling the solution to the laboratory temperature and waiting for 15 minutes to form a bluish-violet product gives the highest absorption at the wavelength of 580 nm compared to the blank solution, which gives a low absorption of 0.0448 at the same wavelength against absolute ethanol (Fig. 4).

Table 9: Optimal conditions for the proposed method.

Type of aldehyde	Amount of reagent (ml)	Type of conc. acid	H ₂ SO ₄ (ml)	Time (min.)	Solvent
2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	2.5	H ₂ SO ₄	1.0	15	Ethanol

Fig.4. Absorption spectrum of 12.0 μg of ATO-Ca as measured (A) vs. blank solution, (B) vs. absolute ethanol, and (C) blank solution vs. ethanol.

3.4. The procedure and standard curve

After fixing the optimal conditions for the determination of ATO-Ca as shown in Table 9, the standard curve was prepared according to the following working method: Add 2.5 ml of 1% 2-HNA reagent solution to 1.0 ml of

concentrated sulfuric acid with gentle shaking, then increasing volumes of 0.01-2.5 ml ATO-Ca (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was added and wait for 15 min at room temperature before complete the volumes to mark with absolute ethanol, the absorbance of the samples was measured against the blank solution at a wavelength of 580 nm after 5 minutes standing. Fig. 5 represents the standard straight curve that is in agreement with Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.1-25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. It was found that the molar absorptivity coefficient of the product was $5.1412 \times 10^4 \text{ l/mol. cm}$ and Sandell's significance was $0.02247 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, and the values of the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitative (LOQ) were $0.0570 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and $0.1902 \mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, respectively.

Fig. 5. Standard curve for the determination of ATO-Ca in its reaction with a reagent 2-HNA.

3.5. The nature of the resulting product

The nature and ratio of the association of the polyhydroxy alcohols with the aldehyde or the ketone in the nucleophilic addition reactions depend mainly on the location of the hydroxyl groups present in the drug compound under study ATO-Ca, as the presence of two hydroxyl groups in an alternating site in each molecule helps to form a hexagonal ring that gives high compounds stability. Continuous variations method (Job's method), according to the following method: A number of solutions are prepared contain different volumes of 0-0.9 ml of ATO-Ca and 0.9-0 ml of 2-HNA reagent, with concentrations of $8.2685 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ for each one then the aforementioned steps were followed in the previously mentioned. The absorbance of the solutions versus blank at a wavelength of 580 nm was measured (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Curve of continuous variation method for the formed product.

As shown in the figure above, the coupling ratio of ATO-Ca with the 2-HNA reagent is 1:2, that is, one molecule of ATO-Ca with two molecules of 2-HNA. For the purpose of verifying this ratio, the mole ratio method was

applied by preparing a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks and the addition of 0.2 ml of ATO-Ca solution ($8.2685 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$), and different volumes from 0.1 to 0.7 ml of 2-HNA solution ($8.2685 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) were added at a concentration of 8.2685×10^{-5} under the same previous conditions and the absorbance reading at the wavelength of 580 nm against the blank solution for each. The results shown in Fig. 7 confirm that the coupling ratio is 1:2.

Fig. 7: Molar ratio curve resulting from the coupling of ATO-Ca with the reagent 2-HN.

The shape of the colored and expected output is as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. The proposed chemical structure for the formed colored product.

3.6. Accuracy and precision of the proposed method

Accuracy and harmonics were calculated for the proposed ATO-Ca estimation method and according to the work method adopted in finding the standard curve for three different concentrations of 2.5, 5, and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ATO-Ca for each of them had five readings. (Table 10).

Table 10. Results of accuracy and precision of the proposed method in estimating ATO-Ca.

Amount of ATO-Ca taken μg (	Recovery %*	RE%	RSD %
2.5	97.0	-3.0	2.008
5	100.2	0.2	1.069
10	98.5	-1.5	1.601

*Average of five determinations.

3.7. The applied part

The proposed method was applied in the determination of ATO-Ca in the pharmaceutical preparations shown in Table 11 by taking different concentrations 2.5, 5, 10 and 15 μg from the drug solutions prepared previously and completing the additions according to the optimal conditions previously studied and supplementing the volume with ethanol in 10 ml volumetric flasks. Then, the absorbance was measured at the optimal wavelength of 580 nm and the recovery percentages were calculated (Table 11).

Table 11: Results of applying the proposed method to pharmaceutical preparations.

Drug	μg taken	μg measured	Recovery* %	Average recovery	Drug contain measured, mg
LipoNeer, 20mg/ tab. PioNeer-Iraq	2.5	2.46	98.4	98.22	19.64
	5	4.93	98.6		
	10	9.57	95.7		
	15	15.03	100.2		
ATEROZ, 10mg/ tab. Bilim ilaç Iraq	2.5	2.47	98.8	97.67	9.76
	5	4.81	96.2		
	10	9.69	96.9		
	15	14.82	98.8		

* Average of three determinations.

The results in table above, indicating that the method has good selectivity confirm the success of the proposed method in estimating Ca-ATO, as the average recovery percentage of the locally produced LipoNeer and ATEROZ preparations are 98.22% and 97.67%, which are within the permissible limits according to the approved pharmacopoeia.

3.8. Method comparison

In the comparison of the method, it relied on choosing t_{test} to find out the degree of conformity between the proposed method and the standard method in the US Pharmacopeia for drug determination and to know the validity of the proposed method in application to pharmaceutical preparations, by calculating the recovery percentages of five samples of solutions for each one of the two pharmaceutical preparations ATEROZ and LipoNeer containing 10 mg per tablet, using the relationship mentioned in reference [22] to find the experimental t value. The results are shown in Table 12.

Table 12. Comparison of the proposed method with the standard method.

Drug	Recovery * %		t.exp.
	Present method	[22]	
LipoNeer, 20 mg/tab., pioneer-Iraq	97.80	99.36	1.082
ATEROZ, 10mg/tab. Bilim ilaç-Iraq	98.37	99.96	1.104

*Average of five determinations.

4- Conclusions

The proposed method was characterized by ease, speed and good sensitivity. The method depends on reacting the reagent 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde with atorvastatin calcium trihydrate in an acid medium to form an acetal

compound soluble in ethanol, stable and gives the highest absorption at the wavelength of 580 nm, and follows Beer's law in the concentration range 0.1-25 µg. / ml. From the results obtained, it was found that the method has high accuracy and precision. The method was successfully applied to the assay of atorvastatin calcium trihydrate in pharmaceutical preparations from different origins.

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